

Research article

Soil quality increases with long-term chabazite-zeolite tuff amendments in arable and perennial cropping systems

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ABSTRACT

The application of natural zeolites to improve soil quality and functioning has become highly popular, but we still miss information about the long-term effects on the soil due to its application. This study assesses the soil quality index (SQI) of three distinct agricultural soil systems 6–10 years after a single application of natural chabazite zeolite as a soil amendment. These soils exhibit different management practices: intensive arable (cereals), intensive perennial (pear) and organic perennial (olive). In the arable system, a zeolite application dosage of 5, 10 and 15 kg m⁻² was tested and compared to unamended soil. In the two perennial systems, an application of 5 kg m⁻² was tested against untreated reference soils. A set of 25 soil physical, chemical and biological parameters linked to soil health and quality were analysed at each experimental site. The dataset was investigated through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to calculate the soil quality index (SQI) using linear scoring.

In the arable-cereal field, the SQI doubled (0.3 to ca. 0.6 for all amendments) in chabazite-amended plots; a dose effect was not recognizable. In both perennial fields, the SQI was significantly higher in the chabazite-amended plots (5 kg m⁻²) with similar increases as compared to the arable-cereal field. At each site, the indicators selected by the PCA were different, indicating that chabazite addition impacted soil quality differently in each cropping system. Overall, the results highlighted a significant increase in soil quality with chabazite amendment, which confirms its potential for increasing soil health in the long-term.

1. Introduction

Organic and inorganic soil amendments have been recognized as a valuable tool to improve the quality of agricultural soils (Factura et al., 2010), since they usually enhance soil fertility by augmenting nutrient and water availability for plants, preventing soil dehydration and sustaining a vivid microbial activity in the soil (Garbowski et al., 2023).

Within natural inorganic amendments, zeolites have been studied for decades as a tool to improve soil physico-chemical properties, control nitrogen (N) transformation rates and promote plant growth (Colella, 1999; Eroglu et al., 2017; Gholamhoseini et al., 2012; Keiblinger and

Kral, 2018; Ming and Allen, 2001; Misaelides, 2011). These minerals are tectosilicates constituted of linked tetrahedra of [SiO₄]⁴⁻ and [AlO₄]⁵⁻, which shares all the oxygens to form a 3D solid framework delimiting open channels and cavities, denoted as extra-framework sites. In most natural zeolites, these extra-framework sites may adsorb a wide range of exchangeable molecules ranging from dissolved cations to gasses and water (Delkash et al., 2015; Yalcuk, 2011; Zhang et al., 2008). Along with their positive effect on ion-exchange capacity, zeolites also show reversible dehydration and molecular sieve properties, since only the molecules that fit the size of the extra-framework sites can undergo ion-exchange processes (Sun et al., 2019). Thanks to these

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characteristics, zeolite minerals have found extensive use in industrial and commercial sectors and recently also in various agricultural settings (Cataldo et al., 2021).

Only a few natural zeolites occur in sufficient quantity and purity to be considered an exploitable natural resource, with the most common being clinoptilolite, mordenite, chabazite and phillipsite (Galli and Passaglia, 2011; Kesraoui-Ouki et al., 1994; Mumpton, 1999a). Within each type of zeolite, the main extra framework of exchangeable cations can vary, generating different compositional series. For example, chabazite-Na, -Ca, -K, -Sr and -Mg have been identified as different varieties of chabazite zeolite (Coombs et al., 1997; Montagna et al., 2010). The same is also valid for other common zeolites such as clinoptilolite, phillipsite, faujasite or erionite. For this reason, a profound geochemical and mineralogical knowledge of the applied material, especially for agricultural applications, is fundamental before any technical application. An example is represented by the recent work of Ghorbani et al. (2022), in which a not specified natural zeolite rich in exchangeable Na was used, which caused an increase in specific absorption and soil dispersion. On the other hand, other studies showed that with the proper typology of natural zeolite, unwanted adsorption/desorption dynamics and the risk of soil dispersion can be mitigated (Ferretti et al., 2018a).

Chabazite-bearing rocks are particularly attractive for agricultural applications because of the very high CEC of chabazite (384 cmol kg^{-1}), easy sorption/release of ammonium (NH_4^+) (Gualtieri and Passaglia, 2006; Mumpton, 1999b) and low Si/Al ratio within natural zeolites. Despite the high commercial and academic interest in the use of this zeolite (Di Giuseppe et al., 2016; Ferretti et al., 2020, 2022; Galamini et al., 2020; Medoro et al., 2022), after years of research and fragmented studies, their long-term impact on soil quality remains unknown. Similarly, little is known also about clinoptilolite zeolite, for which – to our knowledge – only Zhao et al. (2023) recently addressed the long-term (5 years) effects of clinoptilolite addition to soil, evidencing a beneficial effect on grain yield and gaseous N losses from the soil.

Soil quality is defined as ‘the fitness of a specific kind of soil to function within its capacity and within natural or managed ecosystem boundaries, to sustain plant and animal productivity, maintain or enhance water and air quality, and support human health and habitation’ (Laishram et al., 2012). In the context of global change, improving soil health is becoming a central aspect to reach sustainable, carbon (C)-neutral crop and food production as foreseen in the EU Green Deal, the EU soil strategy for 2030 and the proposed EU Soil Monitoring Law (2023/0232(COD)).

As a proxy for soil quality, a soil quality index (SQI) can be calculated as a numerical evaluation of diverse soil properties (Andrews et al., 2002; Bissett et al., 2014; Zhou et al., 2020). The SQI foresees defining a minimum dataset (MDS) selected based on physical, biological and/or chemical soil indicators that are then scored and summed to get a final dimensionless value indicative of the quality of a soil (Andrews et al., 2002). In this regard, principal component analysis (PCA) is a commonly used tool to screen suitable indicators for the MDS by reducing the dimensionality of a given dataset without substantial loss of information (Armenise et al., 2013; Büneemann et al., 2018; Martín-Sanz et al., 2022; Rinot et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2020). The indicators selected in the MDS are then subjected to linear or non-linear scoring and integrated into a single index, the SQI by additive-sum or weighted-sum (Martín-Sanz et al., 2022).

The PCA method is however considered to be site-specific and management-specific and it is suggested to be avoided in dataset with a reduced number of indicators (Andrews et al., 2002).

While the SQI has been used to evaluate numerous agricultural management practices (Amorim et al., 2020; Saurabh et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020), studies evaluating the impact of zeolite amendments are still lacking.

Therefore, this work aims to estimate the SQI in three agricultural field experiments where natural Italian chabazite-zeolite was applied 6–10 years ago. Each experiment involved a different cropping system:

arable (Cereals), perennial conventional (Pear) and perennial organic (Olive). While the arable site received zeolite application dosages of 5, 10 and 15 kg m^{-2} , the perennial sites received 5 kg m^{-2} . While various agricultural practices are believed to minimally affect fundamental soil properties like texture and mineral composition in the short term (Büneemann et al., 2018), the addition of external geological substances to the soil could potentially induce substantial changes in soil physico-chemical properties. In order to evaluate soil quality changes, we evaluated a total of 25 soil physical, chemical and biological parameters related to soil health and functioning. We hypothesized that adding chabazite-zeolite minerals to the soil increases the SQI as compared to untreated reference soils, and a higher SQI is achieved with increasing zeolite application rate.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Field site descriptions

Site 1 ($44^\circ 50' 32.63'' \text{N}$, $12^\circ 5' 44.73'' \text{E}$) consists of a 6.5 ha agricultural field located nearby of Codigoro, 40 km East of Ferrara, Italy (Mastroicco et al., 2016) (Fig. 1). The mean annual precipitation (MAP) is 640 mm year^{-1} while the mean annual temperature (MAT) is 14.6°C in the period 2013–2022 (ARPAE, 2022). The soil is classified as Calcaric Gleyic Cambisol (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015) consists of recent interfluvial silty-clay deposits with neutral to mildly alkaline pH (~ 7.3 in CaCl_2) that were reclaimed (1860–1890) from brackish basins to agricultural lands dedicated to cereal cultivation with mainly a maize/wheat/soybean rotation (Colombani et al., 2016). Fertilization in this field is usually performed with a mixed and split application of urea, liquid swine slurry, ammonium-nitrate, and similar chemical fertilizers at the maximum admissible dosage ($170 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$) allowed by the Nitrate Directive (91/676/CEE) in Nitrate Vulnerable Zones. Irrigation was conducted based on necessity with a jet irrigation system.

In 2012 and 2013, zeolite was distributed extensively on the soil surface (Fig. 2A and B) in a single application and then homogenised via ploughing in the top 35 cm of the soil. Plots ($\sim 0.5\text{--}1 \text{ ha}$) were amended with three dosages, corresponding to 5 kg m^{-2} (Z5), 10 kg m^{-2} (Z10), and 15 kg m^{-2} (Z15) of natural zeolite. A non-amended control plot (UA) was also selected in the experiment design (Table 1). From each of these plots, three subplots were defined to address intra-plot variability. All the plots received the same amount and type of fertilizers since 2015.

Site 2 ($44^\circ 48' 44.3'' \text{N}$, $11^\circ 42' 54.0'' \text{E}$) is located in Codrea, Italy (Fig. 1). The MAP and MAT are 643 mm year^{-1} and 14.3°C , respectively, in the period 2013–2022 (ARPAE, 2022). The soil is a Fluvisol Cambisol (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015) with a loamy texture and a mildly alkaline pH (~ 7.5 in CaCl_2). The soil evolved from an alluvial fan originated by an intertributary channel of the Po River in the proximities of the field. Pear saplings (*Pyrus communis* Cv. *Abate Fétel*, ~ 2 years old) were planted in December 2016 and the zeolite was applied concomitantly. During the planting process, a furrow was excavated, and the zeolite was applied at a dosage of 5 kg m^{-2} with the aid of a fertilizer spreading machine and a tractor (after calibrating the speed and release ratio to meet the required dosage) directly into the furrow and on the excavated soil (localized application; Fig. 2 C, D). After positioning the plants, the furrow was closed by mixing soil and zeolite with a shovel.

The orchard has a within-row spacing of $\sim 1 \text{ m}$ with $\sim 3.6 \text{ m}$ between the rows (intensive cultivation). One plot consisted of 40 plants within 2 adjacent rows. Three plots were treated with natural zeolite at a dosage of 5 kg m^{-2} each, and other three were considered controls, which did not receive zeolite. Fertilization in this field is usually performed with NPK and ammonium sulphate fertilizers at a dosage of $\sim 70 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, while irrigation was conducted based on necessity with a drip irrigation system (Table 1). All the plots received the same amount of fertilizer.

Site 3 ($44^\circ 27' 3.48'' \text{N}$, $11^\circ 23' 30.06'' \text{E}$) is an olive orchard located in

Fig. 1. Geographic location of the three experimental sites.

the Bologna province (Fig. 1). The MAP and MAT of the area are 754 mm year^{-1} and 14°C , respectively, in the period 2013–2022 (ARPAE, 2022). The soil is a Hypocalcic Vertic Calcisol (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015) and shows a sandy-loam/sandy-clay-loam texture (USDA) and pH close to neutrality (~ 7.3 in CaCl_2). The field was selected as one of the three sites to host field experiments in the framework of the ZEOVIA project (Medoro et al., 2022).

The evaluated olive orchard consists of ~ 120 olive trees organized in 6 rows: 3 rows of *Olea europaea* Cv *Montecapra*, *Montebudello* and *Farneto* whose soil was treated with zeolite before transplanting and 3 rows of the same Cvs whose soil was left untreated. The transplanting occurred in March 2017 and 5 kg m^{-2} of zeolite was added beneath each plant (highly localized application, Fig. 2 E, F) during the positioning phase, thus assuring contact with plant roots. Fertilization is manure or manure-based in both amended and control plots (Phoenix, Biouniversal fertilizer, Agriazoto etc.). From 2017 to the present, fertilization dosages in the amended plots are 50 % lower than in the control, as a demonstrative practice part of the experimental setup of the ZEOVIA project (Table 1).

2.2. Natural chabazite tuff

The natural zeolite tuff used in all the field experiments considered in this study consisted of a chabazite-rich tuff quarried in central Italy. The zeolite tuff belongs to the Lithic Yellow Tuff (Sorano Formation) as part of the Latera Volcanic Complex area, which comprises a stratigraphic sequence dominated by pyroclastic rocks (Vezzoli et al., 1987). The interplay between circulating fluids and the vitreous component of these volcanic materials was facilitated by the reactive nature and low Si/Al ratio of the alkaline glass. Additionally, the elevated temperature of the system led to the formation of chabazite and phillipsite crystals (De'Gennaro and Langella, 1996). The quarry from which the zeolite

was obtained is named "Piandirena" and extended in an area of about $60,000 \text{ m}^2$ close to the town of Sorano (Grosseto province, Italy) at $\sim 450 \text{ m a.s.l}$ ($42^\circ 41' 26.52'' \text{N}$, $11^\circ 44' 35.54'' \text{E}$).

Table 2 summarizes the most important properties of the applied zeolite. The quarried rock shows a trachytic composition (Stamatakis et al., 2021) and a prevalent content of chabazite zeolite. The mineralogical composition was found to be constant over a time span of 10 years, as evaluated by Galamini et al. (2023) and Malferrari et al. (2013). Therefore, it can be assumed that the chemical and mineralogical composition of the excavated rock did not change significantly over time and can be assumed similar in all three field experiments.

2.3. Soil sampling

Soil sampling was performed in May 2022 at all three experimental sites in a time frame of a few days. The sampling was performed by collecting the first 30 cm soil layer with a manual soil auger (Eijkelkamp Ecosearch, EN Giesbeek, Netherlands) after removing the large-sized and extremely dry topsoil aggregates in the arable soil and eventual ground vegetation in the perennial fields. In the cereal field (Site 1), three composite samples (replicates) were collected in a random position within each sub-plot of the four considered plots (totalling 12 composite samples). Each of the composite samples was formed by three sub-samples. In the pear field (Site 2), for both zeolite-amended and UA plots, three soil samples were collected along the rows in a random position and united to form a composite sample subjected to analysis (totalling 6 samples). In the olive field (Site 3), three random trees showing similar fitness status (by visual evaluation) were selected per treatment belonging to the cultivar *Farneto*. Three sub-samples were collected around the plant at $\sim 20 \text{ cm}$ from the stem and united to form a composite sample to be analysed (totalling 6 samples). The total amount of soil samples collected in the sampling campaign was therefore 24. At

Fig. 2. Application of the natural chabazite zeolite in the three experimental sites (A and B, Arable-Cereal field; C and D, Perennial-Pear field; E and F, Perennial-Olive field). In site 1, the zeolite was applied over the whole soil surface. In sites 2 and 3, the application was made only in the orchard rows or beneath each single plant.

Table 1

Selected information regarding the experimental setup and management at each site.

Site	Cropping system	Zeolite dose (kg m ⁻²)	Irrigation	Regime	Year of amendment	Fertilizers employed	Fertilization Rate (kg-N ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)
Site 1	Arable Cereals	5, 10, 15	Yes/jet irrigation	Conventional/intensive	2012	Liquid swine slurry + Synthetic fertilizers	85–170
Site 2	Perennial Pear	5	Yes/drip irrigation	Conventional/Intensive	2016	Synthetic fertilizers	~70
Site 3	Perennial Olive	5	No	Organic	2017	Organic fertilizers (manure or manure-based)	~40: Always applied 50% less fertilizer in zeolite plots

Table 2

Chemical and Quantitative Phase Analysis (QPA) of the zeolite tuff used in the field experiments along with particle size distribution (PSD), Particle Density (PD) and cation exchange capacity (CEC). Standard deviation within brackets.

Chemical composition ^a	QPA ^a		PSD ^a		PD ^a g cm ⁻³	CEC ^a		
	%	%	Range (mm)	%		cmol ⁺ kg ⁻¹	cmol ⁺ kg ⁻¹	
SiO ₂	56.99	Chabazite	68.5 (0.9)	5–10	11.3	2.26	Ca ²⁺	146
TiO ₂	0.51	Phillipsite	1.8 (0.4)	2–5	83.1		K ⁺	60
Al ₂ O ₃	16.84	Analcime	0.6 (0.3)	0.8–2	3.85		Na ⁺	7
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.42	K-feldspar	9.7 (0.7)	0.425–0.8	0.42		Mg ²⁺	4
MnO	0.10	Mica	5.3 (0.6)	0.25–0.425	0.21		Total	217
MgO	1.79	Pyroxene	2.9 (0.4)	0.125–0.25	0.10			
CaO	4.91	Volcanic glass	11.2 (1.9)	0.075–0.125	0.21			
Na ₂ O	0.63			<0.075	0.62			
K ₂ O	5.64	TZC ^b	70.9					
P ₂ O ₅	0.21							
LOI ^b	8.97							

^a Chemical composition data from Ferretti et al. (2020) were obtained through X-Ray Fluorescence analysis. QPA and CEC data from Malferrari et al. (2013). QPA was obtained through X-Ray Powder Diffraction followed by Rietveld-RIR refinement, while CEC was obtained by measuring the desorbed cations after exchange with 1N NH₄Cl. PD data were obtained by pycnometry. Particle size data from Ferretti et al. (2019).

^b TZC = Total zeolitic content, LOI = Loss On Ignition.

each sampling point at each field, intact soil cores (volume = 100 cm³) were also collected (3 cores per treatment, 24 in total) to account for soil bulk density and to measure soil greenhouse gases (CO₂, N₂O) and NH₃ emissions in the laboratory.

2.4. Analytical techniques

2.4.1. Determination of soil physical, chemical, and biological characteristics

All laboratory analyses were done on air-dried 2 mm sieved soils except for gaseous measurements that were made on intact cores.

Bulk density was estimated according to Equation (1):

$$BD = dW/V \quad (1)$$

where BD is the soil bulk density (g cm⁻³), dW is the dry weight of soil (105 °C for 24 h) in the cylinder (g) and V is the volume of the cylinder (100 cm³). All soil cores taken for bulk density did not contain any stones or gravel.

Soil porosity was estimated with Equation (2):

$$P = 1 - (BD/PD) \quad (2)$$

where P is the soil porosity and PD is the particle density (assumed 2.65 g/cm³).

The soil pH was measured in 1:5 (w:v) 0.01 M CaCl₂ extracts with a pH meter (WTW pH Inolab level 2 benchtop). For CEC, soil samples were mixed with 0.1 M BaCl₂·2H₂O in a 1:20 ratio (w/v), let to rest overnight, shaken for 1 h in an orbital shaker and then filtered with folded paper filters before analysis with an Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (PinAAcle 900T, PerkinElmer Inc.). For the determination of soluble

major cations (K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺), soil samples were extracted with 1 M KCl and H₂O Milli-Q water, respectively, in a 1:5 w/v ratio followed by 1 h shaking in an orbital shaker at 150 rpm and a filtering step with ashless paper filters. The water extracts were analysed via Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) with a Thermo Electron Corporation X series mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻ contents were estimated in the KCl extracts with the sodium salicylate and vanadium (III) chloride methods, respectively (Galamini et al., 2023; Hood-Nowotny et al., 2010), in 96-well plates with an Enspire microplate reader (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA) at 660 and 540 nm, respectively.

The soil total N and C were measured with a CN elemental analyser Elementar Vario Micro Cube (Elementar, Langensfeld, Germany) operating in a continuous flow mode. The total organic C of the soil was estimated using the method proposed by Natali and Bianchini (2015) by lowering the combustion column temperature.

Microbial biomass C, N and P were estimated with the chloroform-fumigation-extraction technique (Brookes et al., 1985; Vance et al., 1987). For microbial C and N (C_{mic} and N_{mic}), 5 g of fresh soil was extracted with 25 ml of 1 M KCl after 1 h of shaking in an orbital shaker and filtering with ashless N-free paper filters. Another aliquot of 5 g fresh soil was fumigated for 24 h under a chloroform atmosphere in a desiccator. After fumigation, samples were extracted following the same procedure as the unfumigated samples. For microbial P contents (P_{mic}), 2 g of soil was extracted with 20 ml of a 0.5 M NaHCO₃ solution (buffered at pH 8.5) with and without chloroform-fumigation (as above). KCl extracts from fumigated and unfumigated samples were analysed with a TOC-L TNM-L Shimadzu Analyzer (Shimadzu, Japan) equipped with an ASI-L autosampler. Before the analysis, inorganic C was eliminated by

acidification. The C and N extracted from non-fumigated samples represented dissolved organic C and N (DOC and TDN) respectively. The C and N extracted from chloroform-fumigated samples minus those extracted from non-fumigated samples represented the C_{mic} and N_{mic} (no correction coefficients were used). The ammonium heptamolybdate colouration method was used for evaluating the total dissolved P (TDP) in fumigated and non-fumigated samples after a peroxosulfate digestion in the autoclave (Voroney et al., 2007). Analyses were carried out in 96-well plates, and the colouration was measured at 712 nm with a PerkinElmer Enspire spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer). The P_{mic} was obtained similarly to C_{mic} and N_{mic} .

Potential Extracellular Enzymes Activities (EEA) of four hydrolytic enzymes involved in the degradation of C-, N- and P-rich organic compounds were investigated: leucine aminopeptidase (LAP) and N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase (NAG) as proxies for N-acquisition, β -glucosidase (BG) as proxy for C-acquisition, and alkaline phosphatase (PHO) as proxy for P-acquisition. We followed the protocol of DeForest (2009) and German et al. (2011) with minor modifications (Mayer et al., 2022). Briefly, aliquots of 0.5 g fresh soil previously sieved at 2 mm were mixed with 50 ml of 50 mM TRIS buffered to soil pH (7.4). After 60 s of ultrasonication, 200 μ l of soil slurry was transferred to black 96-well microtiter plates in four technical replicates under constant stirring. Further, 50 μ l of the substrate (1 mM for all substrates, dissolved in MilliQ water) was added and the plates were briefly mixed horizontally. After an incubation time of 2 h at 20 °C in the dark, fluorescence was measured on an EnSpire microplate reader (PerkinElmer) with an excitation of 365 nm and an emission of 450 nm. Standard curves were prepared for the Amino-methyl coumarin-based substrate (LAP) in concentrations ranging from 5 to 70 μ M, while standard curve concentrations for Methylumbelliferone-based substrates (NAG, BG, AP) ranged between 1 and 140 μ M. In addition, a 50 μ M standard curve was prepared in pure buffer as in soil slurry for each sample separately to calculate a quenching coefficient. Potential enzyme activities were expressed in nmol g dry soil⁻¹ h⁻¹.

2.4.2. Estimation of trace gas soil fluxes

Intact soil cores were kept at 4 °C until further processing and analysis. Four days before the beginning of the lab incubations, distilled water was added to each soil core to reach 45 % water-filled pore space (WFPS). The cores were then kept at 20 °C in a temperature-controlled incubator for two days. Two days before the measurements, additional water was added to reach 65 % WFPS. Pre-test measurements showed that background soil NH₃ emissions were extremely low and hardly detectable (data not shown); therefore, it was decided to stimulate NH₃ and GHG emissions by the addition of urea at a dosage of 50 kg N ha⁻¹ (or 21.3 mg per core).

For the estimation of CO₂ and N₂O soil fluxes, soil cores were incubated for 24 h in an automated chamber system for incubation of intact soil cores (Deltedesco et al., 2019; Díaz-Pinés et al., 2014; Ferretti et al., 2017; Schindlbacher et al., 2004). The system can host up to 22 steady-state-through-flow chambers (Pumpanen et al., 2004), with a flow rate of 900 ml min⁻¹, and was coupled to a G2301 and a G5131i gas analyser for CO₂ and N₂O detection, respectively (PICARRO, Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA).

For estimating soil NH₃ fluxes, soil cores were incubated in a thermo-isolated system with a capacity for six chambers (Deltedesco et al., 2019; Ferretti et al., 2017). The system is based on steady-state-through-flow chambers with a flow rate of 280 ml min⁻¹, connected to a G2103 NH₃ analyser (PICARRO, Inc.). For both systems, daily fluxes were calculated using 6–8 individual measurements per day.

2.5. Statistical analysis, scoring and SQI calculation

To identify the most appropriate indicators for determining the MDS and then calculating the SQI, we applied the common PCA method (Andrews et al., 2002; Askari and Holden, 2015; Laishram et al., 2012;

Martín-Sanz et al., 2022). PCA works by reducing the complexity of a dataset while preserving its essential information. This method generates new variables known as principal components (PCs), which are uncorrelated, encompass contributions from all original variables, and are organized so that the initial ones retain the majority of the original data variance (Armenise et al., 2013). The analysis was conducted separately for each experimental site, on all the 25 standardized physical, chemical and biological soil attributes to eliminate the effect of different measurement units between the soil indicators (Yao et al., 2014). The standardized variables in the PCA maintain unit-variance, therefore the total variance in the PCA is explained by the number of observed variables (25 in this study). The eigenvalue of a PC indicates its relative contribution to the total variance. To reduce the number of PCs we have selected only the PCs with eigenvalue >1 and that explained >5 % of the total variance (Armenise et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2014; Yao et al., 2014). Before extracting the factor loadings of each variable, varimax rotation was applied to maximize the correlation between PCs and the measured attributes (Shukla et al., 2006; Singh et al., 2014). At this point, the factor loadings, which represent the weights assigned to variables within a specific PC, were utilized to reduce the number of variables selected in the MDS. The most important variables were chosen within those who showed an absolute factor loading value in the range of 10 % from the highest factor loading of each principal component. If more than one variable were identified, the decision on the selection was based on the Pearson correlation coefficient to avoid redundant indicators (Armenise et al., 2013). In this case, the following rules were adopted: 1) if the most weighted factors were not correlated, they were all kept in the MDS; ii) if they were correlated, only the variable with higher factor loading was retained in the MDS (Andrews et al., 2002; Singh et al., 2014).

The obtained MDS was then subjected to a linear scoring method using the approach “the more the better” (Eq. (3)) or “the less the better” (Eq. (4)) attributing a score from 0 to 1 to each variable (Martín-Sanz et al., 2022):

$$SL = \frac{X - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \quad (3)$$

$$SL = 1 - \frac{(X - X_{min})}{(X_{max} - X_{min})} \quad (4)$$

where SL is either “the more the better” or “the less the better” linear score, X is the measured value of a certain variable, and X_{min} and X_{max} are the minimum and maximum of the data distribution.

The SQI was then calculated according to Eq. (5) (Martín-Sanz et al., 2022):

$$SQI = \sum_{i=1}^n WiSi \quad (5)$$

where SQI is the Soil Quality Index, n is the number of variables in the MDS, SL is the scoring obtained from the linear scoring method and Wi is a value between 0 and 1 that corresponds to the weight of each indicator calculated according to Eq. (6) (Martín-Sanz et al., 2022):

$$Wi = \frac{(\%VarPCi)}{(\%VarTotal)} \bigg/ \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\%VarPCi}{\%VarTotal} \quad (6)$$

where %VarPCi is the % of variance explained by the PC for the indicator i , %VarTotal is the total amount of variance explained by all the selected PCs in the MDS and n is the maximum number of PCs selected.

To detect significant differences between zeolite amended plots and the unamended soil at each site, t -test was applied for each measured soil indicator (Table 3). Limited to Site 1, the effect of zeolite dosage on the SQI was evaluated by applying one-way ANOVA and Tukey HSD tests (after verifying data normality and homoscedasticity with Shapiro-Wilk and Levene's tests). We refer to significant differences at the $p < 0.05$

Table 3

Differences in physical, chemical, and biological soil properties between zeolite-amended and unamended soils in three different management systems. Values represent mean (3 replicates) \pm standard deviation. Z15, Z10 and Z5 refer to zeolite application dosages at 15, 10 and 5 kg m⁻², respectively, while UA refers to the unamended soil. “***”, “**”, and “*” indicates significant differences ($p < 0.001$, 0.01 , and 0.05 , respectively) compared to the UA within each site. The presence of “” indicates marginal differences ($p < 0.1$). Dataset from Ferretti et al. (2023).

Indicators ^a	Units	Arable-Cereal (Site 1)				Perennial-Pear (Site 2)		Perennial-Olive (Site 3)	
		Z15	Z10	Z5	UA	Z5	UA	Z5	UA
BD	g cm ⁻³	1.19	1.25	1.24	1.37	1.31	1.38	1.18	1.31
	st.dev	0.07	1.25	0.12	0.16	0.10	0.07	0.08	0.12
pH		7.44***	7.41*	7.33	7.27	7.56	7.52	7.33	7.32
	st.dev	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.06
EC	mS cm ⁻¹	0.47	0.46***	0.51**	0.58	0.40*	0.52	0.33*	0.49
	st.dev	0.09	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.01
CEC	cmol kg ⁻¹	39.46	39.78	41.89**	39.76	24.77	25.74	22.28	20.21
	st.dev	0.64	1.53	0.87	0.68	0.61	1.29	1.19	2.40
TOC	g kg ⁻¹	2.00	1.98	2.36*	1.93	0.97	0.84	0.87	0.67
	st.dev	0.08	0.09	0.16	0.05	0.15	0.03	0.03	0.16
DOC	mg kg ⁻¹	41.12	33.06	47.01	41.87	22.57	19.10	23.09	24.61
	st.dev	2.39	4.53	9.82	8.61	7.95	1.90	6.03	5.98
TN	g kg ⁻¹	0.2	0.22	0.26*	0.23	0.13	0.12	0.09	0.09
	st.dev	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.03
NH ₄ ⁺ -N	mg kg ⁻¹	24.04***	16.46**	6.7	5.41	4.93	3.12	3.74	5.35
	st.dev	11.09	3.05	3.08	1.74	0.61	0.98	1.69	3.28
NO ₃ ⁻ -N	mg kg ⁻¹	81.80*	68.77	102	48.02	33.77	43.11	7.86	6.97
	st.dev	12.98	23.38	38	13.31	15.48	22.33	3.04	1.23
TDN	mg kg ⁻¹	98.88*	80.41	116	56.13	45.85	57.75	9.36	8.93
	st.dev	13.70	32.34	44	22.20	23.21	30.46	2.90	0.79
TDP	mg kg ⁻¹	63.47	56.42	67.71	57.87	39.89	17.64	69.67	73.72
	st.dev	3.67	8.36	13.43	18.98	16.81	4.24	31.18	20.19
P _{mic}	mg kg ⁻¹	11.27	8.01	8.02	9.09	14.91	11.67	14.64	28.53
	st.dev	6.34	1.43	4.89	1.97	6.35	2.25	5.00	28.96
C _{mic}	mg kg ⁻¹	160	154	187	175	142	122	91.3	76.6
	st.dev	11	20	6	21	44	19	28.1	19.8
N _{mic}	mg kg ⁻¹	6.81*	6.08	12.01	11.95	15.73	9.48	16.76	12.59
	st.dev	1.59	3.38	5.23	1.87	7.66	4.09	7.16	6.99
LAP	ηmol g h ⁻¹	228	232	255	268	254	262.1	141	90.1
	st.dev	23	15	32	26	27	27	37	19.0
NAG	ηmol g h ⁻¹	26.53*	24.45*	29.27*	49.62	18.04	16.61	9.18	7.25
	st.dev	6.03	5.20	3.99	10.18	6.22	1.35	0.81	3.09
GLU	ηmol g h ⁻¹	113	102	98.80	129	98.4	70.2	43.6	35.4
	st.dev	24	5	12.50	17	25.00	23.40	10.30	16.90
PHO	ηmol g h ⁻¹	155	136 [°]	131*	173	133	128	69.0	54.1
	st.dev	10	16	18	18	32	14	14	11
Mg ²⁺	mg kg ⁻¹	28.87**	22.32	27.95*	20.91	33.87	28.76	18.70	17.39
	st.dev	2.77	1.52	3.35	1.25	12.01	13.12	3.78	1.46
K ⁺	mg kg ⁻¹	77.60	65.34	80.55	53.71	26.66	11.12	14.86	19.45
	st.dev	13.86	14.47	24.76	18.25	15.98	3.65	4.41	6.46
Ca ²⁺	mg kg ⁻¹	248*	207	253*	182	272*	120	77.8	104
	st.dev	37	25	34	12	66	54	6.3	20
NH ₃ -N	μg m ⁻² h ⁻¹	682	367	420	783	298***	784	564***	965
	st.dev	556	194	178	772	261	274	48	454
N ₂ O-N	μg m ⁻² h ⁻¹	0.16	0.49	0.42	1.12	1.02	0.76	0.90	7.37
	st.dev	0.36	0.76	0.56	1.87	0.86	1.35	1.45	6.25
CO ₂ -C	mg m ⁻² h ⁻¹	16.77	12.90	11.82	11.64	9.03	7.89	5.73	11.59
	st.dev	6.55	1.60	2.55	0.17	2.04	3.03	1.65	4.09
MBQ	mg CO ₂ -C g ⁻¹ C _{mic} h ⁻¹	105	84.3	63.3	67.2	71.1	68.4	67.6	169
	st.dev	43	12.5	12.9	9.5	36.3	37.8	33.3	108

^a BD, Bulk Density; EC, Electrical Conductivity; CEC, Cation exchange capacity; TOC, Total Organic Carbon; DOC, Dissolved Organic Carbon; TN, Total Nitrogen; TDN and TDP, Total Dissolved N and P, respectively; N_{mic}, C_{mic} and P_{mic}, microbial N, C and P, respectively; LAP, leucine amino-peptidase; NAG, N-acetyl-glucosaminidase; GLU, β-glucosidase; PHO, phosphatase; MBQ, metabolic quotient.

level. R (4.3.0) and R studio (2023.06.0 + 421) software was used for the statistical analysis and figure building with packages Agricolae, ggplot2, fmsb, nlme and psych (De Mendiburu, 2014; Ginestet, 2011; Nakazawa, 2023; Pinheiro and Bates, 2023; Revelle, 2019).

3. Results

In the arable-cereal field, the indicators that showed significant differences between zeolite-amended plots and the UA were pH, EC, CEC, TOC, TN, TDN, NO₃⁻-N, NH₄⁺-N, N_{mic}, NAG, PHO, Mg²⁺, and Ca²⁺ ($p < 0.05$; Table 3). Concerning pH, slightly higher values were recorded in Z10 and Z15 compared to the unamended plot with a significant effect due to the amount of zeolite in the soil. EC showed higher values in the

unamended plot and lower values in zeolite amended soils depending on the amount of zeolite, following the trend Z15 < Z10 < Z5. Compared to the unamended plot, TOC, TN and CEC were significantly higher only in Z5, yet not in Z10 and Z15. The contents of exchangeable NH₄⁺-N followed a trend related to the application dosage of zeolite, with highest values recorded in Z15 and lowest values in UA while soil NO₃⁻-N showed higher content only in Z15. Similarly, also TDN was significantly higher in Z15, while the N_{mic} tended to follow an opposite trend, with lower values detected at the highest zeolite dosage (Z15). NAG activity was also found to be significantly affected by zeolite application, with lower values recorded in all zeolite treatments compared to the unamended plot regardless to the amount applied. Similar to NAG activity, also PHO activity showed a tendency in lower values recorded in zeolite-

amended plots, but with Z5 being the only with significantly lower values and Z10 showing only marginal differences.

Concerning soluble cations, only bivalent cations Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} showed significant higher values in Z15 and Z5 plots with respect to the UA.

In both perennial fields, t-tests highlighted significant differences only in very few soil indicators: EC, Ca^{2+} and NH_3 fluxes were significantly higher in the zeolite-amended soil in the Perennial-Pear site, while only EC and NH_3 fluxes were significantly higher in the zeolite-amended soil in the Perennial-Olive site, respectively.

3.1. Variable selection for site 1 (arable-cereal field)

Based on the PCA, twelve dimensions were needed to explain 100 % of the variance (Table S1). However, only the first five principal components showed eigenvalues >1 and explained >5 % of the variance. Therefore, only the first five components were selected for the varimax rotation. The cumulative variance explained by these five dimensions accounted for 84.96 % of the total variance.

The PC1 explained 32.6 % of the variance, and the variables that showed the higher loading on this PC were NO_3^- -N, TDN, Mg^{2+} , K^+ , and Ca^{2+} (Table 4). After checking for significant positive or negative correlations (Fig. 3), TDN was selected as the most relevant variable to be considered for PC1 in the MDS. PC2 explained 24.1 % of the variance in the dataset, and the indicator that was mostly loaded on this PC was NH_4^+ -N. The PC3 explained 12.0 % of the variance with GLU and PHO as mostly loaded variables; PHO was selected for the MDS due high correlation with GLU and higher loading. The PC4 explained 9.97 % of the variance and MBQ was highly loaded on this PC therefore it was selected for the MDS. The PC5 explained only 6.34 % of the variance, and the most loaded variables were NH_3 -N and N_2O -N fluxes, which were both selected in the MDS due to absence of correlation. The resulting MDS for the arable cereal field was represented by the following variables: TDN, NH_4^+ -N, PHO, NH_3 -N, and N_2O -N.

Table 4

Loadings of each variable on the first five rotated principal components and communalities (h^2) extracted from the PCA of Site 1 (Arable-Cereal field). Variables selected for the minimum dataset after checking for correlation and redundancy are highlighted in bold italic.

Indicator	Site 1 (Arable-Cereal field)					h^2
	RC1	RC2	RC3	RC4	RC5	
BD	-0.753	0.290	-0.195	0.235	-0.100	0.750
pH	0.216	-0.679	-0.259	-0.611	-0.163	0.970
EC	-0.148	0.917	0.255	-0.040	-0.050	0.930
CEC	0.323	0.285	-0.525	0.536	0.277	0.830
TOC	0.739	0.215	-0.364	0.362	-0.050	0.860
DOC	0.742	0.383	0.448	0.228	0.060	0.950
TN	0.687	0.216	-0.221	0.471	0.423	0.970
<i>NH_4^+-N</i>	0.050	-0.931	0.090	-0.162	0.178	0.930
NO_3^- -N	0.930	0.090	-0.218	-0.030	0.159	0.950
<i>TDN</i>	0.937	0.020	-0.156	-0.020	0.212	0.950
TDP	0.680	0.060	0.243	0.219	0.547	0.870
P_{mic}	-0.166	-0.552	0.365	0.213	-0.113	0.520
C_{mic}	0.361	0.358	0.090	0.653	0.148	0.720
N_{mic}	0.276	0.442	0.373	0.423	-0.479	0.820
LAP	0.200	0.435	0.491	0.554	0.159	0.800
NAG	-0.550	0.424	0.296	0.368	-0.108	0.720
GLU	-0.139	-0.070	0.835	0.334	0.080	0.840
<i>PHO</i>	-0.240	0.160	0.866	-0.070	-0.020	0.840
Mg^{2+}	0.868	-0.060	-0.173	-0.247	0.020	0.850
K^+	0.851	-0.297	0.117	0.214	0.040	0.870
Ca^{2+}	0.847	0.010	-0.331	-0.231	0.000	0.880
<i>NH_3-N</i>	0.106	0.202	0.605	-0.030	0.726	0.950
<i>N_2O-N</i>	-0.257	0.208	0.080	0.090	-0.744	0.680
CO_2 -C	0.266	0.162	-0.030	-0.840	0.206	0.850
<i>MBQ</i>	0.114	0.030	-0.090	-0.957	0.100	0.950

3.2. Variable selection for the site 2 (perennial-pear field)

Six dimensions were needed to explain 100 % of the variance observed in the dataset of Site 2 (Perennial-Pear field) (Table S2) and only the initial five principal components fulfilled the criteria for consideration in subsequent data processing stages.

The PC1 explained 43.5 % of the variance and the most loaded variables on this PC were TDP, Ca^{2+} , DOC and TOC (Table 5). Only Ca^{2+} was selected for the MDS due to the highest loading and high correlation with the other variables (Table 5, Fig. 3). The PC2 explained 30.3 % of the variance and the most loaded variables of this PC were NO_3^- -N, TDN and CEC. TDN was selected for the MDS due to the highest loading and high correlation with the other most important variables. The PC3 explained 12.3 % of the variance with NH_4^+ -N, NH_3 -N and EC as the variables with the strongest loading. Only NH_3 -N was selected for the MDS due to higher loading and correlation with NH_4^+ -N and EC. The PC4 explained the 9.2 % of the variance, with NAG and BD as mostly loaded indicators. Only BD was selected for the PC4. Therefore, the resulting MDS for the perennial-pear site was constituted by the following variables: Ca^{2+} , TDN, NH_3 -N, BD.

3.3. Variable selection for site 3 (perennial-olive field)

In the perennial-olive field, six dimensions were needed to explain the totality of the variance observed in the dataset (Table S3) and only the first five principal components met the prerequisites to be selected for further data evaluation.

Specifically, the PC1 explained 38.1 % of the variance. The variables that were loaded mostly on PC1 were NH_4 , N_{mic} , most of the enzyme activities (NAG, PHO, GLU) and MBQ (Table 6). After checking for correlation (Fig. 3), GLU as the indicator with the highest loading was selected for the MDS for PC1. The PC2 explained 24.8 % of the variance and CEC was the only indicator significantly loaded on this PC. The PC3 explained 16.5% of the variance, TN, TDN, NO_3^- -N and Mg^{2+} were the most loaded variables on this PC. TDN was selected for the MDS due to its correlation with the other selected indicators and the higher loading. The PC4 explained the 14.4 % of the total variance with only K^+ as significantly loaded indicator on this PC. The PC5 explained the 6.2 % of the total variance with BD and EC as mostly loaded indicators on this PC. Only BD was selected due to higher loading and correlation with EC. The resulting MDS for site 3 was constituted by the following variables: GLU, CEC, TDN, K^+ , BD.

3.4. Determination of the site-specific SQI

Based on the variables selected for each site, the SQI was calculated after applying the linear scoring method (Eqs. (3) and (4)) according to Eq. (5). The rationale used for the scoring method was either “the higher the better” or “the lower the better”, depending on the considerations of both soil productivity and environmental protection as main goals (Table 7).

The scoring of each variable at each site is displayed in Fig. 4 in the form of a radar plot, while in Fig. 5 the SQI are displayed. In the cereal field (Site 1), the SQI in Z5 and Z15 were significantly higher as compared to the UA plot ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4A and B).

Both in the Perennial-Pear and Perennial-Olive fields, Z5 showed a significantly higher SQI compared to the UA plot ($p < 0.05$). In the Perennial-Pear field (Site 2), Z5 gained significantly higher scores mainly thanks to lower BD and NH_3 -N emissions, while the indicators TDN and Ca^{2+} had lower impact (Fig. 4C). In the olive field (Site 3), the difference between zeolite-amended soil SQI and the UA is mainly attributable to the higher scoring obtained in GLU, CEC, TDN and BD while only for the indicator K^+ the UA obtained significantly higher scoring in this site (Fig. 4D).

Fig. 3. Pearson correlation matrixes between the soil indicators at each experimental site (A) Arable-Cereal, (B) Perennial-Pear and (C) Perennial-Olive. White squares show non-significant correlations ($p > 0.05$), while coloured squares indicate significant negative (black scale) or positive (red scale) correlations ($p < 0.05$). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

4. Discussion

Natural zeolites are capable of influencing several soil properties when used as a soil amendment. Zeolites, including chabazite, are known to drive variations in the biogeochemical soil N cycle, mainly by altering the dynamics of NH_4^+ (Dwairi, 1998; Ferretti et al., 2022). This effect is thought to be responsible for observed reductions in NH_3 volatilization in several experiments (Bernardi et al., 2014; Bundan et al., 2011; Ferretti et al., 2017; Galamini et al., 2023). Just recently, chabazite has been shown to mildly reduce gross nitrification rates (Ferretti et al., 2021) and NO_3^- leaching losses (Faccini et al., 2018; Mehrab et al., 2016) as well as short-term microbial N assimilation (Ferretti et al., 2018b). Besides the effects on the N cycle, zeolites have been found to increase soil CEC (Gholamhoseini et al., 2013), reduce organic matter decomposition (Truc and Yoshida, 2011), enhance the dissolution of rock phosphate (Pickering et al., 2002) and decrease both soil CO_2 emissions and the metabolic quotient (Ferretti et al., 2017; Mühlbachová and Šimon, 2003). However, most of these effects have been observed in laboratory incubation experiments or short-term field studies, and no information is available concerning the long-term effects (>5 years) of applying natural chabazite in the field.

Our study highlights the beneficial effect of zeolite amendment on soil quality in the long-term and across sites undergoing different

agricultural management (Fig. 5). Starting from Site 1 (Arable-Cereal field), which was subjected to extensive application of zeolite, the SQI doubled both at the higher and lower dosages (Z15 and Z5) with respect to the UA. Z10 showed a similar trend as Z5 and Z15, yet was not significant due to high variability within replicates ($p = 0.10$). In general, samples from zeolite-amended soils were characterized by more TDN and higher NH_4^+-N , which contributed to a higher SQI scoring (Fig. 4A and B). This agrees well with the observed role of zeolites in enhancing the residence time of NH_4^+ in the soil, increasing the total amount of available N due to a reduction in various pathways of N losses (Omar et al., 2015). This evidence is also supported by the higher scoring obtained for gaseous N losses (i.e., N_2O and NH_3 emissions), which agrees well with previous findings (Bernardi et al., 2014; Ferretti et al., 2017; Zaman et al., 2007). The reason behind the reduction of NH_3 fluxes resides in the capacity of zeolites to trap dissolved NH_4^+ and protect it from immediate volatilization, thus increasing its residence time in the soil (Ferretti et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2022). Apparently, chabazite zeolite can maintain this NH_3 emission mitigation property in the long-term, constituting a meaningful tool to counter NH_3 emission peaks after the application of fertilizers.

Concerning N_2O , the higher average scoring (Fig. 4A–Table 7) in zeolite-amended plots may be the result of several factors: (i) lower N_2O fluxes due to zeolite-induced soil liming (Table 3) (Liu et al., 2022); (ii)

Table 5

Loadings of each variable on the rotated principal components and communalities (h^2) extracted from the PCA of Site 2 (Perennial-Pear field). Variables selected for the minimum dataset after checking for correlation and redundancy are highlighted in bold italic.

Indicator	Site 2 (Perennial-Pear field)					h^2
	RC1	RC2	RC3	RC4		
<i>BD</i>	-0.203	0.108	0.300	-0.893		0.940
pH	-0.162	-0.844	0.171	-0.288		0.850
EC	-0.469	-0.040	0.863	0.163		0.990
CEC	-0.245	0.857	0.376	-0.129		0.950
TOC	0.836	0.080	-0.010	0.537		0.990
DOC	0.910	-0.214	0.259	0.232		0.990
TN	0.687	0.305	0.235	0.606		0.990
NH ₄ -N	0.150	-0.271	-0.907	0.255		0.980
NO ₃ -N	-0.295	0.918	0.182	0.000		0.960
<i>TDN</i>	-0.273	0.938	0.157	0.050		0.980
TDP	0.910	-0.214	0.259	0.232		0.990
P _{mic}	0.817	0.205	0.220	0.480		0.990
C _{mic}	0.420	0.516	0.040	0.718		0.960
N _{mic}	0.699	-0.440	-0.060	0.561		1.000
LAP	0.353	0.369	0.609	0.288		0.710
NAG	0.449	0.258	-0.090	0.846		0.990
GLU	0.811	0.286	-0.153	0.393		0.920
PHO	0.267	0.502	0.080	0.774		0.930
Mg ²⁺	0.080	0.453	-0.466	-0.633		0.830
K ⁺	0.788	-0.219	-0.070	0.492		0.920
<i>Ca²⁺</i>	0.913	0.114	-0.373	0.000		0.990
<i>NH₃-N</i>	-0.030	0.212	0.950	-0.154		0.970
N ₂ O-N	-0.458	-0.729	-0.500	-0.070		1.000
CO ₂ -C	-0.436	-0.637	-0.634	0.020		1.000
MBQ	-0.366	-0.764	-0.388	-0.361		1.000

Table 6

Loadings of each variable on the rotated principal components and communalities (h^2) extracted from the PCA of Site 3 (Perennial-Olive field). Variables selected for the minimum dataset after checking for correlation and redundancy are highlighted in bold italic.

Indicator	Site 3 (Perennial-Olive field)					h^2
	RC1	RC2	RC3	RC4	RC5	
<i>BD</i>	0.283	0.392	0.114	-0.264	0.827	1.000
pH	-0.347	-0.105	0.416	0.795	-0.251	1.000
EC	-0.489	0.438	-0.020	-0.090	0.749	1.000
<i>CEC</i>	0.162	-0.979	0.107	0.030	0.060	1.000
TOC	0.815	0.162	0.153	0.121	-0.522	1.000
DOC	0.252	0.624	-0.207	0.694	0.152	1.000
TN	0.239	0.311	0.865	0.311	0.010	1.000
NH ₄ -N	-0.956	-0.222	-0.149	0.040	-0.113	1.000
NO ₃ -N	0.266	-0.197	-0.937	-0.090	-0.060	1.000
<i>TDN</i>	0.060	0.102	-0.949	0.142	-0.255	1.000
TDP	-0.116	-0.239	-0.681	-0.682	0.030	1.000
P _{mic}	0.342	0.818	0.346	-0.209	0.225	1.000
C _{mic}	0.850	-0.118	0.249	0.234	0.384	1.000
N _{mic}	0.940	0.040	0.020	0.116	0.319	1.000
LAP	0.860	-0.340	-0.344	0.246	-0.268	1.000
NAG	0.878	0.140	0.000	-0.418	-0.183	1.000
<i>GLU</i>	0.963	0.213	0.060	-0.020	0.151	1.000
PHO	0.919	0.010	-0.365	0.050	-0.136	1.000
Mg ²⁺	0.090	-0.120	0.900	-0.306	-0.271	1.000
<i>K⁺</i>	-0.020	0.287	0.250	-0.893	0.241	1.000
<i>Ca²⁺</i>	-0.713	0.362	-0.152	0.452	0.365	1.000
NH ₃ -N	0.208	0.799	0.129	-0.353	0.420	1.000
N ₂ O-N	-0.275	0.856	0.209	0.314	0.223	1.000
CO ₂ -C	-0.800	0.479	0.172	0.254	0.189	1.000
MBQ	-0.901	0.305	0.020	0.307	0.020	1.000

lower fluxes due to limited accessibility by nitrifiers to the NH₄⁺ adsorbed to zeolites (Zaman et al., 2007), although this effect was found to be minimal for chabazite in a previous investigation (Ferretti et al., 2021); or (iii) alteration of soil texture due to the addition of the coarse zeolite-tuff, which could reduce anaerobic microsites for denitrification.

In Site 1, the PHO activity was significantly lower in Z5 and

Table 7

Linear scoring used for each variable considered in the MDS and reason of choice. TLTB refers to “The lower the better”, while THTB refers to “The higher the better”.

Variable selected in the MDS	Linear scoring method used	Reason
TDN and NH ₄ ⁺ -N	THTB	Higher availability and thus potentially better supply for crop growth and the soil microbial biomass.
MBQ	TLTB	Lower MBQ means lower CO ₂ emissions per unit of C allocated in the microbial biomass, which may be indicative of higher microbial C use efficiency.
PHO	TLTB	Lower PHO activity indicates less breakdown of organic compounds for P acquisition and potentially a higher P availability.
N ₂ O-N and NH ₃ -N fluxes	TLTB	Lower N ₂ O and NH ₃ emissions mean lower soil N losses and are beneficial from the climate change perspective, crop nutrition and indicative of higher N use efficiency.
GLU	THTB	Higher GLU activity is indicative of higher microbial activity.
CEC	THTB	Higher CEC express higher retention potential of cations and water in the soil which can promote plant nutrition and mitigate drought and nutrient losses.
BD	TLTB	Lower BD values express lower soil compaction, which is beneficial for crop production. Also, low BD favours water infiltration and decrease potential leaching losses.
Ca ²⁺ , K ⁺	THTB	Higher soluble Ca ²⁺ and K ⁺ are indicative of higher important nutrients available to plants.

marginally lower in Z10, indicating a lower need for this enzyme to mobilize P in the soil and hence probably a higher P availability (Allison and Vitousek, 2005), thus contributing to higher scores for this soil indicator in zeolite-amended soils. Previous studies on P availability with zeolites and rock phosphate highlighted that zeolites can increase the availability of P in two main ways: (i) by increasing soil pH (liming effect) and thus increasing P dissolution and (ii) by reducing Ca²⁺ concentration in soil due to ion-exchange processes, thereby limiting the complexation of P in calcium-phosphates (Aainaa et al., 2018).

The MBQ is an expression of the amount of CO₂ respired per unit of microbial biomass and provides information on the relative C use dynamics carried out by soil microorganisms (Ashraf et al., 2022). In this sense, a reduced MBQ is generally indicative of a higher microbial C-use efficiency and is associated with enhanced biomass growth and subsequently diminished C emissions to the atmosphere (Ashraf et al., 2022). While zeolite application did not affect MBQ values (Table 3), the scoring by zeolite amended soils tended to decrease at increasing zeolite dosages (Fig. 4A). Within the same experimental setting as described here, Ferretti et al. (2017) observed a significant reduction in CO₂ emissions immediately after the application of the zeolites; the same trend however was not observed in this study. This may be explained by a limited or only temporary capacity of zeolite minerals to adsorb CO₂ over time. Natural zeolites are indeed known to and used as a medium for C capturing and storage from industrial gas streams due to their intrinsic selective capacity in CO₂ sorption, also at ambient pressure and temperature (Regufe et al., 2019; Siriwardane et al., 2003). This sorption of CO₂ may result in a temporary apparent reduction of MBQ. It is plausible that this effect on MBQ can be linked to the adsorption/desorption cycles of CO₂ operated by the zeolites which – after reaching the maximum adsorption capacity – cannot adsorb more CO₂ until desorption occurs. In the short-term, the addition of zeolite may lead to immediate sorption of a fraction of the CO₂ emitted. In the long-term however, other factors may override this effect.

Similar to the results from the arable site, the application of natural

Fig. 4. Radar plots of the scoring obtained by each variable at each experimental site. The scoring is relative and ranges from a minimum of 0 to a maximum of 1 according to the criteria displayed in Table 7. The black area is the unamended plot (UA) while the areas in red, blue and yellow are the zeolite treatments at various dosages (Z15, Z10, Z5) at each site. Graphs A-B refers to Site 1 (Arable-Cereal), graph C to Site 2 (Perennial-Pear) and graph D to Site 3 (Perennial-Olive). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

chabazite led to significant and positive effects on the SQI also in the other two sites where perennial crops were established (Pear and Olive) (Fig. 5).

In Site 2 (Perennial-Pear field), the role of chabazite in the mitigation of NH_3 emissions was particularly highlighted, while in Site 3, this soil indicator was not selected in the MDS despite it was one of the only indicators showing significant differences (Table 3).

On the other hand, the effects observed on CEC were less pronounced than expected given the high CEC of the employed chabazite tuff (Table 2). A significant fraction of the variance was explained by the indicator CEC only in Site 3 (Perennial-Olive), which was characterized by a coarser texture and an overall lower CEC compared to the other sites (Table 3). However, CEC at Site 1 exhibited a noteworthy increase only within Z5, concomitant with a rise in TOC. This increase was not observed in Z10 and Z15, where higher quantities of zeolites were applied. This suggests that the heightened CEC in Z5 was likely

associated with the increase of soil organic matter (Oorts et al., 2003) rather than being directly influenced by the CEC properties of zeolites. Other studies indeed already reported that the dilution of zeolites in the soil can mask their effects on soil CEC and other physical properties (Szatanik-Kloc et al., 2021). In this specific case, the absence of evident effects on CEC in the Arable-Cereal and the Perennial-Pear site may also be due to the different application methods of the zeolite. A localized application, as occurred in the Perennial-Olive site, in which the totality of the zeolite was applied in direct contact with plant roots, may lead to higher zeolite concentration in the sampling area rather than in the extensive application as in the arable-cereal site or in the trench application as in the Perennial-Pear site (Fig. 2). In both the perennial sites, the BD contributed significantly to differentiating the zeolite-amended plots to the UA (Fig. 4C and D). In both cases, zeolite amendments contributed to a higher scoring (i.e., lower average BD values) compared to the UA plots. This can be partially explained by the lower disturbance

Fig. 5. Bar plots of the SQI calculated for each site including the global analysis. Different letters indicate significant differences after 1-way ANOVA and Tukey HSD tests at $p = 0.05$ (Arable-Cereal field) and t -test (Perennial-Pear and -Olive fields).

in the perennial cropping system and by the low density of the zeolite-rich volcanic tuff added to the soil, although controversial effects of zeolite application on soil BD have been observed in the literature. For example, Szatanik-Kloc et al. (2021) observed no significant effects of zeolite application on soil BD at low dosages (up to 8 Mg ha^{-1}), while Ravali et al. (2020) measured a decrease in soil BD correlated to the amount of zeolite in the soil (up to 7.5 Mg ha^{-1}).

Chabazite zeolite also had a positive effect on the scoring of GLU activity in the coarse-textured soil of Site 3 (Perennial-Olive). Since GLU activity is often used as an indicator of microbial activity (Chae et al., 2017; Levakov et al., 2021), higher available nutrient contents due to zeolite amendment (i.e. higher scoring in TDN) may have facilitated microbial activity in the relatively nutrient-depleted soil of Site 3. Zeolite amendment may also have played a role in the availability of soluble major cations such as Ca^{2+} (positively impacted in the Site 2) and K^+ (negatively impacted in Site 3) due to their capacity for ion-exchange (Ramesh and Reddy, 2011).

Beside the effects observed within each site attributable to the zeolite application, it is worth noting that the soil type and management (e.g., agricultural regime, fertilizer dosages and type, crop type and/or rotation) at each site have played an important role since the variables impacted by the zeolite amendment were different at each location.

It is known that various soil physical properties can be significantly altered by the agricultural regime and therefore also by the type of crops cultivated. The same is true for soil microbial diversity, which also changes with agricultural management such as fertilization (Daly et al.,

2023; Hartmann et al., 2015). For example, Daly et al. (2023) observed that soil quality increased in perennial system compared to annual cropping due to a decrease in bulk density and an increase in soil total porosity in the 5–10 cm soil layer. The increase in total porosity (which is inversely correlated to the BD) in the perennial cropping was attributed by the authors to an increased microporosity due to greater root density. The fact that, for example, BD did not exhibit such an important role in the arable site as in the perennial sites may also be reconducted to the continuous utilization of heavy machineries and tillage, which promotes soil compaction and aggregate disruption, further masking the effects of the zeolite-tuff addition. Moreover, continuous tillage may have gradually fragmented zeolite particles over time, subsequently diminishing its impact on BD.

Finally, it is noteworthy that across each site, the SQI of zeolite-amended soil consistently reached approximately 0.6 (Fig. 5). This uniformity in SQI values persisted despite the selection of different soil indicators in the MDS across the three sites. Meanwhile, the UA consistently exhibited lower SQI values between 0.2 and 0.4 (Fig. 5). This implies that incorporating chabazite zeolite into the soil may lead to a significant long-term increase in soil quality irrespective of management system and soil texture. Moreover, notably at Site 3 (Perennial-Olive), this rise in SQI was achieved even though fertilizer application was reduced by 50 % following the zeolite application in 2017 until today. This specifically underscores the potential of this amendment practice, particularly in soils with low CEC, to aid in enhancing nutrient retention and consequently improving soil fertility. Taking into account

the various field conditions and management practices at the three sites, it is also notable that the SQI consistently displayed a significant increase with the lower dosage of chabazite tested (Z5). This suggests that the application of 5 kg m⁻² of chabazite-zeolite might be already adequate to achieve substantial long-term soil health improvements.

Therefore, despite the limitations of this study, such as the limited samples and the emphasis on chemical and biological indicators over physical ones, we conclude that utilizing chabazite-zeolite as a soil amendment can effectively improve soil quality for an extended period of time, aligning perfectly with EU soil health objectives.

In light of the increased SQI, conducting an economic evaluation of the amendment practice becomes essential to ascertain its viability for widespread implementation. The current cost of Italian chabazite zeolite-tuff is approximately 200–250 €/ton (indicative cost); however, this cost is subject to considerable variability influenced by factors like zeolite type (clinoptilolite is typically less expensive than chabazite, though its effects on SQI are unknown), policies of the selling company, particle size, transport distance, and more. Given the positive effect on soil health, the application of zeolites may be an economically feasible measure across different cropping systems and application strategies to reach soil health advances proposed by the European Union.

5. Conclusions

This study evaluated the long-term (6–10 years) effect of natural chabazite zeolite amendment in different agricultural management systems (arable cropping and perennial cultures). The outcomes from this study highlighted the general beneficial effects of natural chabazite zeolite which increased the SQI in all sites and under different agricultural managements in the long-term. The SQI was not affected by zeolite dosages in the annual cropping system, suggesting that a low zeolite application dosage (i.e., 5 kg m⁻²) is sufficient to increase soil health.

These results must be interpreted as the specific effects of natural chabazite, without generalizing to other zeolites. Future research must therefore not only focus on filling the gaps in the mechanistic understanding of the zeolite impact on C–N–P cycling in the soil-plant-atmosphere system but should also focus on the data collection from long-term field experiments with different typologies of zeolites and from various pedoclimatic settings to support potential positive effects on soil quality with benefits for the atmosphere and climate mitigation towards more C-neutral farming agricultural systems.

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Data statement

Data is available upon request from the corresponding author.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Giacomo Ferretti: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christoph Rosinger:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Eugenio Diaz-Pines:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Barbara Faccini:** Writing – review & editing. **Massimo Coltorti:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Katharina M. Keiblinger:** Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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